

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	Weight of Hg taken g	Weight of Hg-complex obtained g	Weight of Hg calcd. g	Deviation %
1.	0.005 8	0.015 6	0.005 7	-1.70
2.	0.011 5	0.031 0	0.011 4	-0.87
3.	0.019 9	0.054 2	0.020 0	+0.50
4.	0.039 9	0.108 0	0.039 9	0.00
5.	0.059 8	0.162 5	0.060 0	+0.33
6.	0.099 8	0.268 5	0.099 2	-0.60
7.	0.199 6	0.535 4	0.197 9	-0.85
8.	0.199 6	0.535 8	0.198 0	-0.80
9.	0.399 2	1.070 0	0.395 5	-0.92

Results and Discussion

The results obtained for a series of nine determinations (Table 1) have shown that, except in a case where the amount of mercuric ions was as low as 5.8 mg, the experimentally determined values are within $\pm 0.92\%$ deviation in comparison to the true values, suggesting that the method is useful for the gravimetric determination of mercuric ions within 10–400 mg range.

This method is experimentally easier when compared with other gravimetric methods, namely, the sulphide method which requires extraction with CS_2 to ensure the removal of precipitated sulphur, the thionalide method which necessitates an optimum chloride ion concentration⁴, and the periodate method which imposes complete absence of halide ions⁵.

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Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Uranium(VI) using *N-m-Tolyl-p*-methoxybenzohydroxamic Acid

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N-m-Tolyl-p-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid (TMBHA) has earlier been employed in this laboratory¹⁻⁴ for the solvent extraction of Nb^V,

Ta^V, Ti^{IV}, Mo^{VI} and W^{VI}. All these metals are extracted from highly acidic medium (7–8 *M* HCl) with or without presence of thiocyanate. In continuation of this work, we have used this reagent for the solvent extraction of U^{VI}. The advantage of this method is that U^{VI} is extracted in the pH range 4–6 in contrast to other metals which are generally extracted from highly acidic medium and hence can be separated from these metals. There is no need of adding thiocyanate. The optimum extraction is possible at pH 5.0. Thus U^{VI} can be extracted and separated without any serious interference from most of the metals which are generally associated with it in most of the ores and minerals.

In addition to the extraction behaviour of U^{VI} with TMBHA, we also describe here the preparation and characterisation of the solid metal complex by elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility measurements and ir spectra.

Experimental

The stock solution of uranyl nitrate (A.R. grade) was prepared in double-distilled water and standardised⁵. TMBHA was synthesised by the reported method⁶.

A Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cells was used for spectrophotometric measurements. A Elico pH meter was used for pH measurements. Ir spectra were recorded on a Specord IR-75 at C.I.C., Nagpur. Magnetic measurements were made at room temperature with Gouy balance. Conductance measurements were made using a Toshniwal conductivity meter at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with conventional closed type cell.

Procedure: An aliquot of solution containing about 500 μg of U^{VI} was adjusted to pH 5.0 and the aqueous phase made upto 25 ml. The aqueous phase was shaken for 1 min with 0.025 *M* TMBHA (25 ml) in chloroform. After separation of the two phases, orange-yellow coloured complex was measured spectrophotometrically at 370 nm against reagent blank. The amount of metal extracted was computed from the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

The orange-yellow complex absorbs maximum at 370 nm. The Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range of 10–100 μg of U^{VI} per ml of organic solvent. The molar absorptivity and the Sandell's sensitivity values are $2.5 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.09 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

The extraction of metal commences at 4.0 pH and is optimum in the pH range 5.0–5.1 beyond which extraction decreases. A 25 ml of 0.025 *M* TMBHA is adequate for the maximum extraction.

The complex is stable for 24 h. A 10 min shaking time is found to be sufficient for complete extraction. Of all the solvents used (*viz.* benzene, toluene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform and isobutyl methyl ketone) chloroform was found to give the maximum absorbance and sharp peak at 370 nm and hence used.

Effect of diverse ions and extractive separation of U^{VI} : Uranium was separated from several binary mixtures using the recommended extractions. Nb^V , Ta^V , Ti^{IV} , Mo^VI and W^{VI} could be tolerated to twenty-fold excess of U^{VI} . V^V , Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} could be tolerated to five-fold excess. Most of the alkali and alkaline earth metals do not interfere. The ions which interfere seriously include Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Hg^{II} , Mn^{II} , Ce^{IV} , Th^{IV} and La^{III} . Three-fold excess of Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Hg^{II} , and two-fold excess of Mn^{II} , Ce^{IV} , Th^{IV} and La^{III} are tolerable. Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Hg^{II} were masked with potassium cyanide, and Mn^{II} , Ce^{IV} , Th^{IV} and La^{III} were masked with EDTA. Most of the anions including EDTA, fluoride, thiocyanide and cyanide did not interfere. In order to assess the possible analytical application, the proposed method was used for the extraction of U^{VI} from several synthetic mixtures, *viz.* $U^{VI}-Ce^{IV}-Th^{IV}$, $U^{VI}-La^{III}-Ce^{IV}-Th^{IV}$, $U^{VI}-Co^{II}-Ni^{II}-Hg^{II}$ and $U^{VI}-Ca^{II}-Sr^{II}-Ba^{II}$ prepared by mixing 0.5 mg of each metal with 0.1 mg of U^{VI} .

In all the cases U^{VI} was extracted quantitatively. The relative standard deviation of the method was found to be $\pm 0.9\%$.

Nature and composition of the extracted species: From Job's⁷ mole-ratio⁸ and slope-ratio⁹ methods the composition of U^{VI} to TMBHA is found to be 1:2. This is further supported by the plot of $\log D$ (distribution ratio of metal) vs $\log [TMBHA]_0$ (concentration of TMBHA in organic phase at equilibrium) which gives a slope of two. On the basis of these observations, the probable extractable species formed may be UO_2R_2 , where R stands for the anion of the reagent.

The proposed composition of extractable species and the structure of the complex of U^{VI} with TMBHA were confirmed by studying the elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility measurements and ir spectra of the solid complex.

Preparation of U^{VI} -TMBHA complex: The alcoholic solution of ligand and aqueous solution of uranium were mixed in 2:1 (L-M) ratio and the solution was stirred thoroughly until the brownish red colour developed. After adjusting the pH to about 5.0, a brownish red precipitate appeared which was allowed to settle, filtered and washed first with hot water and then with 50% ethanol. The complex was dried in desiccator over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Structure of U^{VI} -TMBHA complex: The complex was analysed for C, H, N and U contents.

The results correspond to $UO_2(C_{15}H_{14}O_8N)_2$. This M-L ratio of 1:2 was also obtained in chloroform extract of U^{VI} -TMBHA complex. The complex behaves as non-electrolyte ($\Lambda_M = 8.75 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) in DMF medium.

The visible spectra of the complex was recorded in chloroform against solvent blank. The spectra showed no band in the region 400-700 nm indicating no transitions due to f-electron. This indicates f^0 -configuration of the metal ion. The complex was found to be diamagnetic in nature which supports f^0 -configuration and hence it confirms octahedral geometry.

Ir spectra shows that a band at 3100 cm^{-1} which is due to OH disappears in the spectra of complex. The band due to C=O stretching vibration (1625 cm^{-1}) in the free ligand is displaced towards lower frequency (1600 cm^{-1}) in the metal complex. The C-N stretching frequency ($\sim 1400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the free ligand is found to be displaced towards higher frequency on complexation. These observations show that coordination of hydroxamic acid occurs through oxygen of C=O group. The band due to N-O stretching vibration (940 cm^{-1}) in free ligand gets shifted to higher frequency (1020 cm^{-1}) on complexation. The bonding of carbonyl oxygen to metal atom has been further confirmed by the observed M-O stretching frequency at 442 cm^{-1} . The presence of uranium-oxygen covalent bond in the complex was established. The complex exhibits a very strong band at 920 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to asymmetric stretching of uranyl ion in accordance with the earlier^{10,11} observations in many uranyl complexes ($900-950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Thus U^{VI} is octahedrally coordinated to two ligand molecules and two oxygen atoms.

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